

INTEGRATION OF SOLAR PHOTOELECTRIC-THERMOELECTRIC HYBRID SYSTEMS, MODELING METHODS AND OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Solar panels can only convert a certain part of the solar spectrum into electricity, the rest is lost as heat. This leads to overheating of the panels and, as a result, a decrease in their efficiency [3]. Therefore, it is important to study the possibilities of using the excess heat of solar panels and converting it into electricity. To overcome this problem, studies have been conducted on the integration of photovoltaic (PV) and thermoelectric generator (TEG) systems, the first of which was presented by Kasimakhunova A.M. and one of the last [1].

PV-TEG systems have the following advantages:

- Maximum solar energy utilization – excess heat generated by sunlight is converted into electricity [4].
- No heat dissipation and cooling – TEGs prevent PV panels from overheating, which extends their service life [4].
- Sustainable power supply – Some advanced systems are being developed with phase change materials (PCMs) that allow 24-hour operation [5].

For optimal performance of solar PV-TEG systems, there are the following important issues and their scientifically based solutions:

Device Compatibility and System Parameter Optimization.

Power Management and Global Maximum Power Point (GMPP) Tracking.

Thermal management and passive cooling technologies.

Optimization based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML).

Configuration adaptation in PV-TEG systems.

Solar PV-TEG hybrid systems are one of the promising technologies that allow maximum use of solar energy. To improve their efficiency, new thermoelectric materials, artificial intelligence algorithms, and advanced thermal management technologies are needed. In the future, it is advisable to continue research in the following areas:

- Development of new thermoelectric materials
- Wide use of artificial intelligence technologies
- Testing systems in real conditions